

PROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF COMBINED RADIATION THERAPY FOR LOCALLY ADVANCED CERVICAL CANCER IN KASHKADARYA REGION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13834813>

Abstract. *This study is based on the results of treatment of 52 patients with locally advanced cervical carcinoma. Recidive-free and overall annual survival of patients and the influence of certain factors on survival rates were analyzed. Analysis of the results of combined radiation therapy for locally advanced cervical cancer shows that the overall annual survival rate is $98.1 \pm 0.8\%$, recidive-free survival is $69.2 \pm 1.7\%$. It has been established that most recidives occur during the first 6-9 months after initial treatment. The influence of some factors of the body and tumor on the period of observation was revealed, such as reproductive age, stage of the disease, damage to the parametrium, immediate results of treatment and the degree of radiation pathomorphism.*

Keywords: *cervical cancer, world health organization.*

Actuality. Cervical cancer (CC) is one of the most common tumors of the female reproductive system. According to WHO, about 470,000 new cases of cervical cancer are detected annually in the world. Every year, almost 250,000 women die from this disease [4].

About 1,851 cases are detected annually in Uzbekistan, and about 115 cases of cervical cancer in Kashkadarya region. Common tumors account for almost 1/3 of all identified cases [1]. Over the last decade, there has been an unfavorable picture of an increase in patients at a young age with a widespread tumor process, which significantly reduces the results of their treatment. Despite the relatively satisfactory (42.4%) 5-year survival rate of patients with locally advanced CC, a fairly large number of patients in this category die from disease progression, tumor recidives and metastases [2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

Over the past decades, new methods of radiation therapy for cervical cancer have emerged: the introduction of 3DCRT-3D, IMRT and VMAT, adaptive radiation therapy, planning of intracavitary irradiation using CT/MRI images, combining interstitial and intracavitary radiation therapy, replacing the intracavitary stage of radiation therapy with a remote component with sequential or simultaneous escalation of the dose to the cervix when brachytherapy is not possible.

Modern equipment and planning systems allow high doses to be delivered to the tumor, and intracavitary radiation therapy to be performed under visual control of the target and organs at risk. The combination of intracavitary and interstitial radiation therapy provides the opportunity for better coverage of the target with a dose, maximally excluding organs at risk from the irradiation zone.

Replacing the intracavitary stage of radiation therapy with a remote component can make it possible to deliver a cancericidal dose to the tumor when intracavitary treatment is not possible.

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EXTENSION BEAM THERAPY OF THE FIRST STAGE OF A COMBINED COURSE

As part of the combined course, before the start of EBRT, a pre-radiation preparation stage is carried out, which includes the selection of the patient's positioning using individual fixing means, CT/MRI topography, target and risk organ contouring, selection of the total dose and fractionation mode, radiation therapy planning and verification of the irradiation plan [8].

During the EBRT stage, treatment is carried out daily (from Monday to Friday) for 5 weeks (22-28 procedures). It is preferable to start the EBRT course on the 1st day of the week [8][9]. The standard single dose is 1.8-2.0 Gy, the total dose for the course of external beam radiation therapy is 46-50.0 Gy.

MODERN BRACHYTHERAPY FOR CERVICAL CANCER

Brachytherapy provides better local tumor control compared to the use of only a course of EBRT due to the maximum concentration of the dose in the tumor volume. The local irradiation volume receives the maximum dose, almost equivalent to the total dose achieved from the remote irradiation stage. Contact methods of dose delivery involve the use of a radioactive source that is in close proximity to the tumor, and taking into account the inverse square law, according to which the radiation dose is inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the source, a dose with a high value (> 80 Gy) is absorbed in the tumor volume with low radiation loads on the surrounding normal structures [8][10][11]. The superiority of EBRT over standard EBRT techniques (conventional and conformal EBRT) is explained by the dose distribution, which is characterized by a low integral dose and a high gradient of dose drop, allowing for a maximum reduction in healthy tissue while delivering a high dose to the irradiation target. On the other hand, the radioactive source loaded into the applicator located in the target volume eliminates the need for additional indentation to account for errors in positioning and adaptation when changing the filling of the bladder and rectum [10][11].

The purpose of the research: To prospectively study the effectiveness of combined radiation therapy in patients with locally advanced cervical cancer.

Materials and methods: Combined radiation therapy according to a radical program, as the only method of treatment, was carried out in 52 patients with locally advanced CC in 2023. The age of the women ranged from 31 to 72 years, median 49.25 ± 1.53 years.

The diagnosis was confirmed morphologically in all patients. The predominant histological type is the squamous cell variant of cervical cancer, which was diagnosed in 94.6% of cases: 23.2% of patients had non-keratinizing squamous cell carcinoma, and 71.4% had keratinizing squamous cell carcinoma. Adenocarcinoma was found in three patients (5.4%).

FIGO stage II was established in 21 (40%) women, stage III was diagnosed in 28 (53.8%) cases, and stage IV B was diagnosed in 3 (5.8%) patients.

When analyzing the obtained clinical data, recurrence-free and overall, 1-year survival of patients was assessed (according to Kaplan-Meier), and the influence of certain factors on survival rates was also assessed [3]. Statistical calculations were performed on a personal computer using the SPSS v license package. 15.0.

Results and discussion: The average total focal dose to point "A" was 87.13 ± 0.95 Gray with a minimum of 85 and a maximum of 98.96 Gray. Most patients received a total focal dose to point "A" from 85 to 88.5 Gray.

The average total focal dose to point "B" was 58.16 ± 0.79 Gray and ranged from 51 to 74 Gray. The vast majority of patients - 62.5% received from 53 to 65 Gray at point "B", more than

65 Gray were given in 19.6% of patients. In 17.9% of cases, the total focal dose to point “B” was less than 53 Gray.

The results of treatment were monitored in 52 patients. The average follow-up time for this group of patients was 6.33 ± 0.2 months. Median follow-up – 6 months. The maximum observation period was 15, and the minimum was 3.8 months.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, by the end of the year of observation there is a slight change in overall survival compared to recurrence-free survival after combined radiation therapy in patients with locally advanced CC.

Of the total number of 52 patients, 33 ($63.46 \pm 1.2\%$) patients had no symptoms of disease recidive, and 19 ($36.54 \pm 1.2\%$) patients had disease recidive. Overall survival is $98.1 \pm 0.8\%$, recurrence-free survival of patients after combined radiation therapy is $69.2 \pm 1.7\%$,

Fig.1

Patients with recidive from Fig. 2 shows that the frequency of recidives by the end of the year of observation decreases, the timing of recidive was determined in 13 patients from 6-9 months. (68.5%), in 6 patients up to 10-12 months. (31.5%).

Fig.2

We assessed the effect of reproductive age on treatment outcomes. Thus, better outcomes of the disease were identified in women who were in a state of menopause. These data, in our

opinion, deserve attention and further study. Thus, differences in survival begin already from the end of the first year of observation and amount to $94.7 \pm 5.1\%$ in women of menopausal age and $6.0 \pm 6.6\%$ in the reproductive period.

The clinical stage of the disease, as an indicator of the extent of the tumor process, has a significant impact on the results of combined radiation therapy (Fig. 3). We did not analyze separately the treatment results for stages II A and III A due to the small number of patients. But a comparison of recidive-free survival rates for stages II B and III B revealed statistical significance of the differences: $85.0 \pm 8.4\%$ and $62.3 \pm 12.1\%$ for 2023 follow-up, respectively.

Fig.3

Conclusions: Thus, an analysis of the long-term results of combined radiation therapy for locally advanced CC showed that overall survival is $98.1 \pm 0.8\%$, recidive-free survival is $69.2 \pm 1.7\%$. It was revealed that the largest number of recidives occurs in the first 6-9 months. after completion of treatment. The influence of reproductive age, clinical stage, parametrium involvement, and immediate clinical effect on long-term treatment results has been established.

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